

CREEP AND RUPTURE BEHAVIOR OF ADVANCED SiC FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

To address the thermomechanical stability issues observed in first-generation fibers, a variety of advanced SiC fibers with improved microstructures have been recently developed. The objective of this study was to use creep-rupture measurements in air from 1200 to 1400°C in order to assess improvements in mechanical stability for four advanced fiber types: Hi-Nicalon, Dow Corning, Carborundum, and SCS-X. Using empirical models to mathematically describe the creep-rupture data, it is shown that these new SiC fibers should increase ceramic composite use temperatures by at least 100°C over those available from the first-generation Nicalon and SCS-6 fibers. The results also suggest the optimum polycrystalline SiC fiber should have a flaw-free microstructure that is pure and stoichiometric with a tailored grain size somewhat less than 1 μm .

INTRODUCTION

An important key to the technical success of structural ceramic matrix composites (CMC) is the development of continuous-length small-diameter SiC fibers which display high stiffness, high strength, and good retention of these properties under oxidizing conditions to temperatures well above 1000°C [1]. Although SiC in pure, stoichiometric, and coarse-grained bulk form exhibits good mechanical and oxidative stability up to 1400°C, undesirable losses in creep resistance and load-bearing capability have been observed below 1000°C for first-generation SiC fibers, such as Nicalon and SCS-6 [2]. The underlying degradation mechanisms are apparently related to the intergranular sliding of submicron-sized grains aided by low-viscosity grain boundary impurity phases introduced during fiber production. These impurity phases are suggested to be silicon-oxycarbide in the polymer-derived Nicalon fiber and free silicon in the chemically vapor-deposited (CVD) SCS-6 fiber [1].

The objectives of this study were (a) to determine the extent to which four types of newly-developed SiC fibers with improved microstructures minimize the thermomechanical stability issues observed in the first-generation fibers and (b) to project the high temperature strength performance of CMC reinforced by these advanced fibers. The approach taken was to measure fiber creep strain and rupture time in air from 1200 to 1400°C. Using simple empirical equations to model the experimental results, creep and rupture strengths for each fiber type were then calculated and compared for a typical CMC application.

EXPERIMENTAL

Production information and as-produced properties for the four advanced SiC fibers and the first-generation Nicalon and SCS-6 fibers are listed in Table I. The advanced fibers include: (a) the commercially available Hi-Nicalon fiber from Nippon Carbon which like Nicalon is polymer-derived with very fine-sized β -SiC grains (~ 4 nm) and a high content of free carbon (~ 40 wt.%), but unlike Nicalon has a significantly reduced oxygen content [3]; (b) a developmental polymer-derived and sintered β -SiC fiber from Dow Corning which is fine grained (~ 100 nm) and near-stoichiometric [4]; (c) a developmental powder-derived and sintered α -SiC fiber from Carborundum which is also stoichiometric but coarse grained (~ 2000 nm) [5]; and (d) an experimental CVD-derived SCS-X fiber from Textron Specialty Materials which like SCS-6 is produced with fine β -SiC grains (~ 100 nm) and a relatively large diameter, but unlike SCS-6 is near-stoichiometric on the carbon-rich side [6].

Table I. PROPERTIES OF AS-PRODUCED SiC FIBERS

TRADE NAME	ADVANCED				FIRST-GENERATION	
	HI-NICALON	DOW CORNING	CARBORUNDUM	SCS-X	NICALON	SCS-6
MANUFACTURER	NIPPON CARBON			TEXTRON SPECIALTY MAT'LS	NIPPON CARBON	TEXTRON SPECIALTY MAT'LS
AVAILABILITY	COM-MERCIAL	DEVELOP-MENTAL	DEVELOP-MENTAL	EXPERI-MENTAL	COM-MERCIAL	LIMITED
PROCESS	POLYMER-DERIVED	POLYMER, SINTERING	POWDER, SINTERING	CVD	POLYMER-DERIVED	CVD
MAX. PROCESS TEMPERATURE	~ 1300 C	> 1600 C	> 1800 C	< 1400 C	~ 1300 C	< 1400 C
COMPOSITION (WT.%)	β -SiC 0.5% O 36% C	β SiC TRACE C TRACE B	α SiC TRACE B	β SiC TRACE C (20 μ m C CORE)	β SiC 12% O 31% C	β SiC TRACE Si (33 μ m C CORE)
AVG. GRAIN SIZE (nm)	4	~ 100	~ 2000	~ 100	2	~ 100
DENSITY (g/cm ³)	2.7	3.1	3.1	2.8	2.6	3.1
AVG. DIAMETER (μ m)	14	10	28	50	14	142
ELAST. MODULUS at RT (GPa)	270	400	420	320	220	390
TEN. STRENGTH at RT (MPa)	2800	3200	1300	6000	3000	3500

For the creep-rupture studies, individual as-produced fibers of ~ 18 cm length were mounted on paper grips, hung vertically in a ~ 10 cm-long furnace with molybdenum-disilicide elements, and dead-weight loaded at temperature in ambient air. Measurements were made of (a) fiber creep strain versus time and (b) the time for fiber fracture or rupture. The primary variables held constant during the test were the applied stress and the fiber temperature in the ~ 25 mm long furnace hot zone. Details of the test rig and the creep and temperature measurements are given elsewhere [7]. For convenience, test runs on fibers that did not rupture were terminated after ~ 100 hours. Applied stresses were determined from the dead-weight load and optical measurements of the average diameter for the fiber section in the furnace hot zone. Negligible change in fiber diameter was observed even after 100 hours at 1400°C.

The choice of a 25 mm hot section for the fiber creep-rupture tests was based on rule-of-mixtures (ROM) composite theory which not only describes stress distribution between composite constituents, but also fairly accurately predicts composite strength from fiber strength. That is, if σ_f and σ_m are the average in-situ stresses on the fiber and matrix, respectively, then the total composite stress σ_c is given by

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f^* + \sigma_m (1 - V_f^*) \quad (1)$$

where V_f^* is the effective fiber volume fraction aligned in the composite stress direction. Likewise, if σ_f is the average fiber tensile or rupture strength measured at 25 mm gauge length and σ_m is the stress on the matrix at composite fracture, then σ_c in Eqn (1) is a good approximation for the composite ultimate tensile or rupture strength. Curtin [8] and others have shown this to be the case because the fiber average strength measured at 25 mm closely approximates the fiber bundle strength at the fiber critical transfer length in both ductile and brittle matrix composites. Thus fiber creep strength and rupture strength results from this study can be used directly in Eqn (1) to predict CMC ultimate creep and rupture strength.

Besides grain size and impurity phases, another Table I property of particular importance for this study is the maximum production temperature for each fiber type. Whereas the sintered fibers were produced well above 1400°C (the maximum test temperature employed here), the Hi-Nicalon, SCS-X, Nicalon, and SCS-6 fibers were not. This implies that the test temperature in itself can change the microstructures and properties of these latter fibers. Indeed, pre-exposures of the advanced Hi-Nicalon and SCS-X fibers to temperatures above their maximum process temperatures have been shown to improve creep resistance and degrade room temperature strength [6,9,10]. Thus the time-dependent creep-rupture effects observed in this study for as-produced Hi-Nicalon and SCS-X fibers may in part be due to microstructural annealing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CREEP BEHAVIOR

Typical creep curves for the six SiC fiber types are shown in Fig. 1 for the same test conditions, i.e., 270 MPa at 1400°C in air. Clearly it can be seen that all the advanced fibers do indeed display creep resistance better than the first-generation fibers. For effectively all test conditions employed in this study, the fibers ranked in the following order of decreasing creep resistance: Carborundum, SCS-X, Dow Corning, Hi-Nicalon, SCS-6, and Nicalon. Also seen in Fig. 1 is the fact that creep rates for all fibers continuously decreased with time until fracture, giving the appearance of only a primary or transient creep stage to strains of 1% or more. As mentioned earlier, part of this transient effect in some fibers may be related to microstructural annealing at the test temperature. Nevertheless, even the sintered fibers showed transient behavior, suggesting that at these temperatures a relatively large primary stage may be intrinsic to all SiC fiber types. Since many CMC applications require creep strain limits below 1%, it follows that measurement and analysis of this stage would have both basic and technical significance.

For all fiber types, it was observed that creep strain (ϵ , %) increased with stress (σ , MPa), time (t , hours), and absolute temperature (T , kelvin) in a manner that followed very closely the following empirical equation [11]:

$$\epsilon = A \sigma^n t^p \exp[-B/T] \quad (2)$$

Here the fiber-dependent creep parameters A , n , p , and B were found to remain effectively constant within the envelope of test and strain variables for this study: that is, time from 0.1 to 100 hours, temperature from 1200 to 1400°C, stress from 100 to 1000 MPa, and creep strain from 0.1 to 1%. Best-fit empirical values for the four parameters for each fiber type are listed in Table II. The approach used to determine the parameters was to hold two of the three test variables constant at their mid-range values and then perform linear regression analysis on appropriate data plots of creep strain versus the third variable. Although it may be possible

Figure 1. Typical creep curves for advanced and first-generation SiC fibers.

Table II. CREEP-RUPTURE PARAMETERS FOR AS-PRODUCED SiC FIBERS

FIBER TYPE	CREEP PARAMETERS ^a				RUPTURE PARAMETERS ^a		
	A	n	p	B	E	$\beta \times 10^4$	D
Hi-NICALON	1.4×10^6	1.8	0.58	42100	7.8	1.4	22
DOW CORNING	3.2×10^4	2.1	0.75	41000	6.3	1.0	22
CARBORUNDUM	2.5×10^7	1.0	0.48	44200	4.8	0.6	22
SCS-X	3.0×10^{-2}	1.1	0.38	9247	5.7	0.7	22
NICALON	4.0×10^3	1.2	0.40	24200	6.0	1.0	22
SCS-6	5.0×10^3	1.1	0.37	25800	4.6	0.5	22

a Best fit to Eqns (3) and (4) with strain = %, stress = MPa, time = hr, temperature = kelvin

to correlate the Table II creep parameters with microstructural features like grain size and grain boundary phases [12], such analysis is beyond the scope of this study. Nevertheless, from the Table I information and the relative creep behavior of the six fiber types, it can be concluded that creep resistance increased with increasing purity, stoichiometry, and grain size.

As discussed in a later section, another convenient approach for evaluating the creep behavior of the various fiber types is to determine the time/temperature dependence of their creep strength, $C_r(\epsilon^*)$, which is defined as the applied stress that is needed for a fiber to reach a certain critical creep strain limit, ϵ^* . By Eqn (2), it follows that

$$C_r(\epsilon^*) = \{ (\epsilon^*/A) t^p \exp[B/T] \}^{1/n} \quad (3).$$

It should be noted that for Eqns (2) and (3), the Table II empirical parameters apply only for constant stress and constant temperature conditions. Also, since the parameters were determined with currently available data for as-produced fibers tested in air, they can be subject to change as data bases increase, production approaches improve, and fibers are pre-treated and tested under conditions which simulate those inherent in CMC fabrication and use [11].

RUPTURE BEHAVIOR

In contrast to the fairly consistent behavior observed for fiber creep, fiber rupture time showed much more scatter. This effect could not be attributed to the air test environment because rupture times were typically equal to or longer in air than in inert environments [7]. Despite the scatter, it was still possible to use the rupture time data to evaluate the rupture performance of the six SiC fiber types. For example, Figs. 2a and 2b are log-log plots for applied stress versus rupture time for each fiber type at 1200 and 1400°C, respectively. Such plots are convenient for three reasons. First, since fiber rupture strength S_f is defined as the applied stress that causes fiber fracture in a constant stress test, the plots are in fact practical data for fiber rupture strength versus stress application time. Second, as log-log plots, they allow simple application of ceramic rupture theory which predicts an inverse power law relationship between S_f and rupture time [13]. Finally, by plotting log of rupture time, the data scatter is much reduced, allowing easier averaging. Typically 3 to 6 rupture-time data points were available to draw the best fit straight lines for each fiber type (see, for example, Ref. 11).

Examination of Fig. 2 reveals some important trends concerning fiber rupture strength. First, as temperature increased, all fibers showed a greater time rate of strength degradation. This behavior can be contrasted with the temperature-independent degradation rate observed for fiber creep strength [cf. Eqn (3)]. Second, the rupture rate generally correlated with the creep resistance of the fiber; that is, the greater the creep resistance, the smaller the time rate of rupture strength degradation. Third, it would appear that the best performing fibers in terms of absolute strength capability were those which were the strongest at room temperature and displayed limited creep at the temperature range of interest. Thus up to 1400°C, the SCS-X

Figure 2. Log stress (rupture strength) versus log rupture time for SiC fibers measured in air at (a) 1200°C and (b) 1400°C. For clarity, actual data points are not shown (cf Ref.11), but have been averaged by straight lines according to ceramic rupture theory.

fiber clearly outperformed the weaker but more creep resistant Carborundum fiber. Above 1400°C, however, this may not be the case because the rate of strength degradation for the more creep-prone SCS-X fiber should be greater than that of the Carborundum fiber. This trend can also be seen for the even more creep-prone Hi-Nicalon fiber which was stronger than the Carborundum fiber up to 1200°C, but about equal in strength at 1400°C.

To summarize the rupture behavior, although the advanced fibers showed improved creep resistance and generally reduced strength degradation rates, if these improvements were achieved at the expense of a low as-produced tensile strength, absolute strength capability across a wide temperature range may be worse than that of more creep-prone fibers. This appears to be the case for the Carborundum fiber where the source of its superior creep resistance is its coarse-grained structure which is also the source of its low as-produced strength [5]. Reducing grain size should improve the Carborundum strength, but should also degrade its creep resistance. Thus the optimum polycrystalline SiC fiber for high strength up to ~1400°C would appear to require a flaw-free microstructure that is pure and stoichiometric with a tailored grain size somewhat less than 1 μm (see also Ref. 14). At the present time, the CVD SCS-X microstructure is probably the closest to this goal. However, the potential of this microstructure for CMC reinforcement is currently limited because it only exists in relatively large diameter fibers that display limited flexibility for CMC fabrication [1].

Finally, as with creep strain and creep strength, it is useful for design purposes (see next section) to empirically model fiber rupture strength as a function of time and temperature. The observations that strength degradation rates appear constant for log-log plots at a given test temperature and that the absolute value of these rates increase with temperature suggest the following empirical model [11]:

$$\log S_r = E - \beta q \quad . \quad (4)$$

where $q = T(\log t + D)$, and E , β , and D are empirically determined rupture parameters. The time/temperature-dependent variable q and constant parameter D are similar to the Larson-Miller variable and constant, respectively [15]. Eqn (4) was best fit to rupture strength versus time data for at least two test temperatures to determine the three rupture parameters which are listed in Table II for each fiber type. Since the data was found to be insensitive to the value for D , the same average value was chosen for all fibers ($D = 22$). As discussed above, the degradation rate parameter β appeared to decrease with increasing fiber creep resistance.

CMC IMPLICATIONS

A more practical method for assessing the thermomechanical capability of the advanced SiC fibers is by examining the results of this study from the viewpoint of projected CMC performance. As with other high temperature structural materials, the mechanical properties that will usually be examined first by a component design engineer are the CMC creep strength and rupture strength for the component's service time and temperature. Generally the lower value between creep and rupture strength will limit the maximum stress that can be applied on the CMC. Today, however, there exists a lack of analytical theory which allows easy calculation of CMC strengths from fiber properties. This is the case because due to mechanisms such as creep and microcracking, the constituents within CMC can be subject to complex time-varying stresses, even with a constant stress on the CMC. One approach to circumvent this issue is to assume that throughout the CMC service life, the stress carried by the matrix is effectively zero. This assumption may not be unreasonable since it is likely that during early CMC service the matrix will rapidly stress relax due to creep rates greater than that of the fiber, or the matrix will multiply crack due to high initial stress [14].

Under the assumption that the matrix carries no load, conservative calculations of CMC creep and rupture strengths can now be made from Eqn (1) with $\sigma_m = 0$ and $\sigma_f = C_f(\epsilon^*)$ or S_f . To illustrate use of this approach, one might assume a typical CMC application which requires a service life of 1000 hours and a creep strain limit of $\epsilon^* = 1\%$. Then by Eqns (3) and (4) and the creep/rupture parameters of Table II, one can calculate the temperature-dependent curves in Figs. 3a and 3b for fiber 1%-creep strength and rupture strength, respectively. Dashed lines were used in Fig. 3a to indicate those temperature conditions were the fiber's creep strength is greater than its rupture strength; that is, when the fiber rupture strain is below $\epsilon^* = 1\%$. To use these plots, a design engineer might then select a certain CMC steady-state service stress and CMC architecture (that is, V_f^*) to calculate by Eqn (1) a required fiber strength. For example, assuming a 100 MPa (~15 ksi) composite stress and $V_f^* = 20\%$ (as for a typical two-dimensional CMC with total fiber content of 40%), the minimum required fiber strength is 500 MPa (~70 ksi). By Fig. 3, the SiC fibers would then rank in the following order of maximum temperature capability (* = creep limited): Dow Corning and Hi-Nicalon (~1160°C*), Carborundum (~1130°C), Nicalon (~1030°C*) for the small-diameter fibers; and SCS-X (~1270°C*), SCS-6 (~1170°C*) for the large-diameter fibers. Clearly these temperature estimates will not only be dependent on the CMC application but also on the accuracy of the fiber models to predict strength inside and outside of the envelope of test conditions. For the Table II parameters, error analysis within the test envelope indicates temperature errors of less than 20 and 50°C for the predicted creep and rupture strengths, respectively.

With the above illustration, one can see a variety of advantages for the fiber strength models. First, they can be used to determine under what conditions the advanced SiC fibers outperform the first-generation fibers. For example, under the service conditions assumed above, it would appear that the new fibers can provide at least 100°C improvement in CMC use temperatures over first-generation fibers with similar diameters. Second, the models can provide initial estimates of maximum use temperatures for CMC reinforced by each fiber type. This in turn should allow design engineers to better select potential fibers for a particular application. Third, the models show whether creep or rupture limits fiber performance. This should allow fiber manufacturers to better focus their efforts toward improved microstructures.

Figure 3. Projected temperature-dependent curves for the 1000-hr (a) 1%-creep strength and (b) rupture strength for advanced and first-generation SiC fibers. Dashed lines are used to estimate creep strength behavior beyond fiber rupture.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

When SiC fiber types of similar diameter are compared, the results of this study show that the four advanced SiC fibers: Hi-Nicalon, Dow Corning, Carborundum, and SCS-X are clearly more creep resistant than the first-generation Nicalon and SCS-6 fibers. These creep improvements, which are primarily due to purer and coarser-grained microstructures, are also observed to provide reduced time/temperature-dependent rates of strength degradation. Thus, for those advanced small-diameter fibers with high room-temperature strengths (> 3000 MPa), the mathematical creep-rupture models developed here predict that for a typical 1000-hr application, stress-dependent CMC use temperatures should range up to $\sim 1300^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is at least 100°C higher than that available from the first-generation Nicalon fiber. It should be mentioned, however, that two of these advanced small-diameter fibers (Dow Corning and Carborundum) are still in a developmental stage during which their manufacturers are using data such as those presented here in order to further improve fiber use capabilities for CMC.

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